

Roberto Marcucci, Francisco E. Baralle, Maurizio Romano

Complex splicing control of the human Thrombopoietin gene by intronic G runs

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Allegations: Figure 3D lanes 1, 3 and possibly 4 are 'much more similar than expected'.

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/8F64D842FD7A39731F4FBFF3E3DA50#1>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/8F64D842FD7A39731F4FBFF3E3DA50#2>

<https://imgur.com/mnNizok>

↑ Figure 3D as published in NAR

↑ Cropped Fig3D following Equalize adjustment.

↑ Cropped Fig3D following Levels adjustment.

↑ Cropped Fig3D following Edges filter.

↑ Cropped Fig3D following Gradient Map adjustment.

↑ Cropped Fig3D following Gradient Map adjustment.

↑ **Cropped Fig3D following Gradient Map adjustment.**

In conclusion: The bands are indeed very similar but there are subtle variations in shape, intensity and artefacts. There are no signs of splicing. Overall, the Editors believe this image to be genuine.